

Theoretical Explanation of Sustainable Security Paradigm in Border and Border Regions

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Abstract

Border security is the protection of border lines against possible attacks and the prevention of any illegal acts along the border and border areas of a country, and the legalization of the movement of people and the transportation of goods through authorized border gates. Establishing security at the border and border areas is one of the main concerns of countries, especially in today's world full of threats, and governments consider different approaches, policies, measures and methods to achieve this goal. The concept of “sustainable security” is derived from new security paradigms and approaches in various areas, including border security and border areas. In fact, “sustainable security” is an approach proposed in recent security studies as an alternative to the “control paradigm” and is based on the principle that in order to deploy security instead of dealing with crime, the context of the crime must be tackled. This article presents the requirements and considerations of the deployment of security at the border and border areas in the framework of paradigm “Sustainable Security” using a descriptive-analytical method and citing reliable sources. The findings of the research indicate that the establishment of stable security at the border and border areas requires preventive, positive, comprehensive, community-oriented, participation-oriented, comfort-giving and meaning-oriented approaches, and based on this paradigm, border security with the priority of ensuring the security of border residents achieved.

Keywords: Border, Border Regions, Sustainable Security, Development, Paradigm

Introduction:

International borders, as they are the most important factor in distinguishing the sovereign territory of a political system and separating independent countries from each other, hold a very important role and position (Rahmati Rad, 1995: 54). Establishing security in borders and border regions has been one of the main concerns of governments from the distant past until now, and countries have taken various measures in this direction (Akhbari and Nami, 2009). The formation and organization of armies and military forces, the establishment of border posts and military stations at borders, the creation of border governance systems such as Ghassan and Hira, the construction of walls and defensive barriers at borders such as the Great Wall of China, Hadrian's Wall, and the Gorgan Wall, the forced displacement of human groups and tribes, the conclusion of non-aggression treaties between neighboring countries, and so on have been among the most important strategies of governments for establishing security at their borders (Zarghani, 2019: 8).

Various components and factors are effective in border security and border management; these components can be divided into four dimensions: economic (development of border regions, financial management, adaptive management...), socio-cultural (border police community, participation and strengthening of border communities, human resource management...), political-governmental (management of joint border patrols, joint border centers, joint databases, organizational management, customs management...) and technological-security (optical, radar, wireless sensor network and technological management...) (Ahmadi, Saleh Abadi, 2020: 44). In fact, what is generally agreed upon today is that having secure and safe borders plays a decisive role in implementing good neighborliness policy and exercising the sovereignty of any government in any country, and has extensive applications in economic, political, and military arenas (Zolfaghari and Soltani, 2014: 42). Nevertheless, it seems that currently, many countries' borders, especially in developing regions, suffer from insecurity. The creation of massive and expensive border closure plans and wall construction in recent years along the borders of many countries such as the United States-Mexico, Iran-Afghanistan, India-Pakistan, Kuwait-Iraq, Saudi Arabia-Yemen, Turkey-Syria, Turkmenistan-Uzbekistan, North Korea-South Korea, and others demonstrates that despite the trend of globalization and the idea of the "death of borders," the protection of borders and ensuring border security of countries are still considered among the main considerations of governments (Zarghani, 2018: 4).

In classical security schools and approaches, establishing security was predominantly achieved through force with the help of military tools, and the main reference of security was the state and political system. On this basis, since the type and main source of threat was the military factor, countries strengthened their military forces and armament power to counter this threat (Poursaeed, 2013: 34). This type of perspective also dominated the establishment of security at countries' borders, and for this reason, we still see the concentration of military forces and military and law enforcement centers and stations at many countries' borders; which, using hardware-oriented methods, combat manifestations of border threats such as unauthorized crossings, human trafficking, smuggling of goods, drug trafficking, mischief, conflict, and so on. However, global conditions and developments have changed, and it is necessary to manage borders accordingly. In today's globalized world, border management is one of the biggest challenges facing various governments; governments that ask themselves how security can be maintained alongside encouraging and facilitating trade, and how to overcome the contradiction between economic welfare based on the free flow of goods, people, and services while simultaneously monitoring and controlling them, and how to prevent smuggling of goods, human trafficking, illegal immigration, and worse than those, organized crime and terrorism? (Kardan, 2020: 92). During the last two or three decades, we have witnessed the emergence of a new paradigm in the field of security under the title of "sustainable security." Compared to past security schools, in this paradigm we are faced with different foundations, characteristics, and indicators. Essentially, the emergence of the concept and paradigm of "sustainable security" is a continuation of the developments that have taken place in the field of security over the past decades, and in fact, sustainable security is an approach that is presented in modern security studies as an alternative to the control paradigm (Rastegar Panah and Soltani Far, 2012: 77).

literature review

Regarding the study of sustainable security in Iran's border regions, various research has been conducted, which is briefly mentioned: Sarvar et al., in their article titled "Spatial Analysis of Development Indicators in Achieving Sustainable Security in Border Regions," examined the relationship between development and sustainable security in northwestern border regions. This research focused on the impact of sustainable development indicators on border security in the studied regions and, based on these indicators, divided the border regions into four groups including very privileged, privileged, semi-privileged, and underprivileged

(Sarvar et al., 2015: 1-22). Mousavi et al., in their article titled "Prioritizing Indicators and Components of Sustainable Security in Border Regions of Khorasan Razavi Province," prioritized the components and indicators of sustainable security in the border regions of Khorasan Razavi Province. The research findings show that, firstly, there is a significant correlation and relationship between the components in question, and secondly, in terms of ranking, the economic security component, the social and cultural component, the political component, and finally the defense-security component have had the greatest role in shaping sustainable security in the border regions of Khorasan Razavi Province, respectively (Mousavi et al., 2017: 57-93). Jalalian, in his article titled "Investigating Factors Affecting the Promotion of Sustainable Security in Border Regions: Case Study of Sardasht Border County," used a survey method to examine and analyze factors affecting the promotion of sustainable security in the Sardasht border region. The research findings show that the Sardasht border region has witnessed an increase in smuggling of goods and hostile militant groups in recent years, which has caused insecurity in the region. Results from the field study indicate that the security situation in the Sardasht border region is in an aggressive SO (Strength-Opportunity) position (Jalalian, 2019: 61-86). Norouz Zadeh, in his article titled "Designing a Sustainable Border Security Management Model in Ardabil Province," has attempted to propose a model for managing sustainable border security with emphasis on supporting Iranian-made products. The research findings indicate that the expansion of economic factors, elimination of economic poverty, increasing the capacity of border regiment forces, and creating sustainable jobs in villages (given the multiplicity of border villages) are among the most important factors in creating sustainable security and preventing smuggling of goods at the borders of this province (Norouz Zadeh, 2022: 157-190). Bazrafshan and Toulabi Nejad, in their article titled "Analysis of the Effects and Functions of Social Capital in Sustainable Security of Villages in Border Regions of the Central District of Saravan County," analyzed the role of social capital in establishing sustainable security in villages of the border regions of Saravan County. The research findings show that the increase in social capital has had the greatest impact in the social dimension and has led to an increase in the preservation of linguistic patterns, preservation of culture and religion, reduction of drug use among youth, reduction of conflicts and disputes among residents, and so on. Also, in the political-military security dimension; participation, trust and cohesion among residents, and cooperation and participation with law enforcement and border guards have led to increased political participation of people, reduced ethnic and tribal divisions, reduced illegal travel to neighboring countries, increased cooperation with military forces in fighting outlaws and smugglers, and

establishing order and security (Bazrafshan and Toulabi Nejad, 2016: 55-76).

Qader Marzi et al., in their article titled "Evaluation of Effective Components in the Security Sustainability of Border Regions," examined and evaluated factors affecting sustainable security in border regions. The research findings show that seven main components including economic-social components, physical environment, the role of government, transformation of border function, level of accessibility, urban security, and media performance have a significant impact on regional balance and sustainability of border regions (Qader Marzi et al., 2018: 203-228). Finally, Pir Ali and Siadat, in their research titled "NAJA's Strategies in Developing Sustainable Security in the Eastern Border Regions of the Country in South Khorasan Province," have attempted to study the most important challenges and threats to law enforcement in establishing and developing sustainable security in this province and to present appropriate solutions for developing sustainable security. The findings of this research show that three main strategies including: 1. Synergy of law enforcement-security capacities at the provincial level; 2. Development and implementation of a comprehensive border security plan with the participation of people and border residents at the provincial level; 3. Increasing cooperation with other relevant organizations to develop economic and social infrastructure, have had the greatest impact, respectively, in developing sustainable security in the eastern border regions of the country by the law enforcement forces (Pir Ali and Siadat, 2013: 31-52).

Theoretical Foundations

International Borders:

Among various types of borders, international borders hold a special position in terms of importance, scope, and function. This is both because they determine the territory of government and the exercise of power and sovereignty, and because they encompass a large number of people or nations (Zarghani, 2019: 20). In fact, international borders are an expanded form of those conventional lines that humans have determined to mark the periphery of their domain, in the surrounding part of their environment or territory. This peripheral line, which marks the final part of a nation's domain and has taken on a political aspect, is called a "border" (Mojtahedzadeh, 2008: 31). Some scholars, like Drysdale, have emphasized the function of borders in their definition and consider borders as a spatial phenomenon that reflects the territory of a state's political sovereignty and, according to specific rules, creates barriers against human movement, transfer of

goods, spread of ideas, etc. (Drysdale, 1995: 101). Others, like Muir, who is among political geographers, emphasized describing its characteristics in defining borders: "Borders have been described somewhat as linear things. In fact, borders come into existence where the vertical interfaces between state sovereignties pass through the earth's surface" (Muir, 2000: 281). Similarly, some scholars like Mirheydar emphasized the most important function of borders in their definition: "Political borders are the most important factor in identifying and separating one political unit from others, and border lines are conventional and contractual lines that are determined on the ground to delimit a political unit" (Mirheydar et al., 2017: 95). Finally, it can be said that international borders are political-spatial phenomena that conventionally and in the form of a vertical cut, determine and separate the sovereign territory of independent political systems (Zarghani, 2013: 22).

Defensive and Communicative Functions of International Borders:

The most important and oldest function of international borders is to define the boundaries of sovereignty and the exercise of political will of governments from one another. In addition, functions such as separation, integration, differentiation, communication, conflict (Hafeznia, 2000: 190; Prescott, 1978: 18), creation and strengthening of political unity, shaping political and economic relations between states (Rahmati Rad, 1995: 8) are considered other functions of international borders. Of course, as Glassner says, the role and function of borders change over time, and today advanced technologies have reduced the value of the defensive function of borders, and most states do not believe in strengthening their borders to ensure their security (Glassner, 2004: 80). In fact, with the developments that have taken place in the world today, the traditional concept of borders and their functions has changed. Thus, the concept of border has transformed from a single border to multiple borders, from a line to a region, from physical to cultural, from spatial to functional, and from impermeable to permeable (Golverdi and Ghavam Maleki, 2015: 83). Generally, from the perspective of border interactions, the function of international borders can be classified into two groups: a) The communicative-commercial function of the border, b) The defensive-security function of the border (Zarghani, 2007, 117).

Figure 1. Two perspectives and two spaces; the border as a 'wall' and the border as a 'bridge', Zargani, 2016: 47

A) Communicative-Commercial Function:

The first function of a border is its communicative-commercial function. As shown in the figure above, in the communicative function, the border acts as a communication bridge that facilitates commercial, social, cultural, tourism, and other connections between the people of two countries, especially border residents. In the communicative function, the dominant perspective is economic. That is, unlike the defensive-deterrent function of the border, where we seek to strengthen the impermeability of the border and the dominant view is security-political; the dominant approach in the communicative function is economic and commercial. Therefore, we are looking to answer the question of how to use the border as a means of connection between two neighboring countries. The goal is to play a role in expanding the connection between people on both sides of the border and increasing commercial, human, cultural, and tourism exchanges through actions such as creating border gates and crossings, establishing border markets, establishing free trade-industrial zones at common borders, and so on. In the communicative function and the approach to the border as a bridge, borders do not hinder imports and human relations, and although borders distinguish the territories of different sovereignties from each other, they essentially create good political, economic, and cultural relations between neighboring states. Just as in the ordinary life of families, the shared wall of neighbors is not a barrier to coming and going and socializing but is a factor of friendship and cooperation, the border of neighboring states is also a valuable geographical factor that plays a major role in strengthening bilateral relations (Motamednejad, 2005: 87). In fact, the border areas of states have a major position in neighborly relations, and especially during periods when relations between two neighboring states are good, the effects of these relations are more noticeable in areas adjacent to the border. In critical

situations, considering that border residents may have an understanding with the neighboring state due to common language or religion, or they may be pessimistic about it due to historical precedents resulting from military attacks, they might cooperate with or strongly oppose the neighboring state. However, often because there are kinship interests and trade relations between border residents on both sides, friendly relations are generally maintained between people living on both sides of a border. It is for this reason that in some countries, border residents are sometimes considered to be supporters of foreign policies and are viewed with suspicion (Hafeznia, 2006: 6).

B) Defensive-Security Function of the Border:

The second function of a border is its defensive-security function. If borders are viewed as phenomena that define the territory of a government's sovereignty and power over its people and resources under its influence, while preventing the influence, intervention, and use by the government and people of the neighboring country. From this perspective, the most important function of a border is to create a barrier and deterrent factor. This means that borders prevent the entry and exit of any phenomenon that interferes with the exercise of power and sovereignty of that country.

Figure 2. Defensive-Security Function of the Border: Border barriers on the right (Spain – Morocco / left Turkey – Bulgaria)

In the deterrence function of the border, the political-security perspective is dominant, and therefore we are seeking to answer the question of how, by carrying out various measures including creating physical barriers, installing electronic equipment, defining buffer zones, establishing military and law enforcement centers, and the like, the border can be made increasingly into an impenetrable barrier, resulting in border security. Generally, if borders are viewed as a barrier, at least four functions can be identified for them: The role of the border as a defensive

barrier, The role of the border as a political barrier, The role of the border as a social barrier. Finally, the role of the border as an economic barrier (Dwivedi, 1990: 141-42)

Concept and Definition of Security:

The term security has a long history as old as human history. According to historical accounts, the need for security and the necessity of feeling safe has been the main concern of humans even before the emergence of human societies; to the extent that God in the Quran mentions security as one of His blessings. The term "security" is derived from the word "secure." In Persian language, equivalents such as safe, protected, assured, to secure, not being exposed to danger, or being protected from danger have been used for it. The lexical definitions of this word include protection against danger (objective security), feeling of safety (subjective security), freedom from doubt, freedom from anxiety and fear, and having justified and documented trust and confidence (Rabiee, 2004: 44). In dictionary definitions, the dual nature of the concept of security is well reflected, as on one hand it means safety, stability and impermeability, reliability, confidence in not failing, and on the other hand, it means absence of anxiety from distress and danger (Abdollahkhani, 2004: 357). The term "security" first became extremely common in American political literature. Then, the important changes that occurred in international politics after World War II caused this concept to become more functional.

Security is defined as the feeling of freedom from fear or a sense of safety that oversees both material and psychological security, and the main elements of security observed in most definitions of security are values, risks, or threats (Eftekhari, 2004: 312). In fact, two approaches—negative and positive—are proposed in defining the nature of security; the first considers security as equivalent to the absence of threat, while the second defines security as the preservation of values and equality of opportunities. Within this framework, Barry Buzan, a prominent expert on security issues, after conducting studies on the presented definitions, defines security as "freedom from threat" and believes that security is understood in the absence of another issue called "threat." In his view, security relates to the capacity of states and societies to maintain their independent identity and territorial integrity (Abdollahkhani, 2004: 136). In fact, in these types of perspectives, security policy is directed toward achieving maximum military power to overcome enemies (internal and external) and acquire security. Alvin Toffler articulated the symbolic slogan of this approach from Mao Zedong as

"power comes from the barrel of a gun" (Setareh, 2011: 16). It should be noted that the concept of security as traditionally used is based on two important assumptions: 1- Threats to states, whereby security threats fundamentally emerge from external borders, and 2- These threats are fundamentally, if not exclusively, military in nature and usually require a military response (Sayigh, 1998: 29). From the variety of definitions provided regarding the concept of security, it is clear that there is no general consensus on the definition of security. The reason for this is that, according to experts, security is an ambiguous, subjective, relative concept that can be abstracted by elites and is defined in an environment where threat exists; therefore, we should never expect a single and absolute definition of "security."

Concept and Definition of Border Security:

Border security refers to: "Protection of conventional lines established for the terminal part of the environment's perimeter of a political unit, against potential encroachments designed and implemented by other actors" (Eftekhari, 2006). Additionally, in defining border security, it has been stated: "Border security means preventing any illegal acts along a country's borders and legalizing the movement of people and transportation of goods and domestic animals in compliance with legal regulations and through authorized border gates" (Khattabi, 1995: 85). As evident in the above definitions, in border security we encounter terms and concepts such as "protection" and "prevention," therefore it can be said that there is a direct relationship between border permeability and border security (Zarghani, 2016: 44). In other words, if border control is difficult in terms of preventing the entry and exit of people, goods, etc., and the potential for unauthorized traffic and smuggling of goods, drugs, etc. increases, we say the border has greater vulnerability (Sotoodeh, 2010: 14). Several factors can be mentioned for border security and its manifestations and indicators; the most important of these indicators are:

- Movement of persons through official and unofficial gates in accordance with approved regulations
- Transportation of goods through authorized gates and in accordance with customs regulations
- Prevention of drug trafficking and other unauthorized goods across unauthorized borders
- Cooperation between border guards of neighboring countries in various agreed areas
- Maintenance of border tranquility and absence of border conflicts and disputes

- Existence of legal communications and exchanges between people on both sides of the border
- Implementation of border laws and regulations for border officials and others
- Based on these factors, indicators of insecurity and border threats can also be examined (Setareh, 2011: 56).

Concept and Definition of Sustainable Security:

The most important need of society, whether a tribe or a country, is the provision of security by governments. Today, with societies becoming more extensive and complex, the subject of security has taken on extensive and complex dimensions to the extent that past approaches to security no longer have the necessary comprehensiveness (Mousavi et al., 2015: 35). Historically, during the Cold War, power was defined in military terms, and security was naturally one-dimensional and understood from a military perspective. However, in the era of globalization, with the multiplication of power in political, social, cultural, economic, technical knowledge, individual, and technological domains, security has also undergone a multidimensional definition and change. Security in the globalization era is based on a concept of systemic security in which security is part of a network interconnected with other components of that network, and the entirety of the network continuously affects its individual components (Alaei, 2012: 123). In fact, today we are facing a new paradigm called "sustainable security" that pays attention to all dimensions and indicators of security and emphasizes the fair spatial and social coverage of security and the pivotal role of people in establishing security (Zarghani and Bakhshi, 2016: 12). This new paradigm has a different perspective on security and has its own dimensions, characteristics, and specific indicators. Sustainable security cannot be achieved solely through military measures but is redefined within the framework of the new demands of contemporary citizens that have taken on regional, national, and transnational dimensions. Sustainability and its compound concepts, such as sustainable security, refer to a comprehensive understanding based on which all effective political, social, cultural, security factors, etc., are considered alongside each other and in interaction with each other.

"Sustainable security," like the concept of security, is a complex and multifaceted concept, and therefore there are different and multiple perspectives on its definition, nature, elements, function, dimensions, and characteristics. In fact, the category of sustainable security is an interdisciplinary concept; therefore,

recognition and reaching a relatively comprehensive definition is not possible without considering social sciences, economic sciences, political sciences, and cultural studies. The contribution and role of each of these sciences in conceptualizing and semantics of new sustainable security is not the same. Sustainable security is an interdisciplinary category for two reasons: one, due to the interconnectedness, intertwining, and multilateral relationships of social, cultural, political, and economic phenomena with each other, which is itself due to the networked nature of today's societies; and second, due to the bilateral relationship of the category of "sustainable security" with the set of social, cultural, political, and economic phenomena (Fatehi, 2012: 110). In the following, the definitions of sustainable security and its theoretical foundations are briefly mentioned:

Sustainable security is a type of socialized, culture-oriented security that can respond to a set of material and non-material needs of individuals, social groups, and sovereignty (state and government) with the lowest social cost and the highest social reward (Fatehi, 2012: 107). Another definition portrays sustainable security as a state and considers it a situation where all factors continuously work to prevent fundamental values from being attacked, and in the event of an attack, whether cultural, political, or military, these values are not sacrificed for peace but are defended (Norouzi, 2006: 141). Some scholars have taken a result-oriented approach in defining sustainable security and equate it with creating a balanced, secure, and growing society in material and spiritual aspects based on innate human values through the systematic application of all cultural, political, social, economic, and security components (Rastegar Panah and Soltani Far, 2012: 79). In addition, some experts consider sustainable security as a type of security that enhances the capability of societies to prevent or defend against threats to the nation-state; reduces deep human insecurity around the world; and manages long-term threats to global security. In fact, in this sense, sustainable security is a combination of three concepts: national security, human security, and global security, and aims to preserve the security of states without endangering the security of people and without aggravating threats to global security such as AIDS, environmental threats, terrorism, and organized crime (Poursaeed, 2013: 34). Some other experts have emphasized the security reference in defining security and consider sustainable security to include environmental protection, respect for people's rights and individual freedoms, and psychological security (Fatehi, 2012: 107). In contrast, some scholars define sustainable security as preserving independence, territorial integrity, safeguarding national ways of life, and preventing foreign interference in internal affairs (Gheisari, 2013: 74).

Figure 3: Frameworks of Sustainable Human Security

Source: Tavanti, 2013: 8

In terms of elements and components of sustainable security, emphasis can be placed on two important components: "freedom from fear" and "freedom from want." These two pillars extend sustainable security across various dimensions of political, economic, social, environmental, food, individual security, and communications. In fact, sustainable security emphasizes a more modern concept of security that is based on the needs of the new world and a fundamental change from the current perspective on security. It is a concept that encompasses the globalization of security and is built on the common characteristic of people worldwide, namely humanity. Therefore, sustainable security is a combination of three approaches: national security or the safety of nation-states; human security or better life and safety for people; and global security or the common interests of all people on Earth (Poursaeed, 2013: 36). The main indicators of sustainable security can include development, welfare, democracy, rule of law, equality and justice, long-term stability, government legitimacy, quality of life, and people-centeredness. Among these indicators, two indicators—"quality of life" and "people-centeredness"—are more important, and in fact, sustainable security is primarily based on human security. Achieving sustainable security requires maintaining moral authority and striving to overcome common security threats more than relying on conventional power (Ghasemi, 2012: 10).

Figure 4: Dimensions and indicators of sustainable security

Approaches and Models of Sustainable Security:

The emergence of the concept and paradigm of "sustainable security" continues the developments that have taken place in the field of security over past decades, and in fact, sustainable security is an approach that is presented in modern security studies as an alternative to the control paradigm. Various theories and models have been presented to explain security issues, and on this basis, various schools of thought have emerged (Rastegar Panah and Soltani Far, 2012: 77). Historically, realist security theory, liberalist security theory, the Third World security school, and the Copenhagen school are classified together as positivistic and traditional security approaches. Although the Copenhagen school initiated changes in the traditional security approach, and the Third World school examines security from a different angle and focuses on Third World security issues, reaching some conclusions that contradict the foundations of traditional security studies, the dominant spirit of these schools remains positivistic and traditional. What is certain is that in all security schools, security was sought for security's sake, or development was sought for security's sake, and security was viewed more in terms of preserving the interests of powers rather than security for human growth, awareness, and the elevation of humans and human society. However, in the sustainable security paradigm, we face some fundamental changes in security

components. In sustainable security, instead of confronting threats, identifying and addressing the processes leading to insecurity becomes important, and by controlling and engineering these processes, the emergence of insecurity is prevented (Oxford Research Group, 2010: 28).

In other words, unlike traditional schools and approaches that were generally dominated by the "control paradigm" and based on the assumption that insecurity could be controlled through military force or a policy of balance of power or containment, and consequently, the status quo could be maintained, the central premise of the sustainable security paradigm is that not all consequences of insecurity can be successfully controlled; instead, the causes must be addressed, and a problem-solving approach must replace problem control or so-called "containment" (Poursaeed, 2013: 27). Furthermore, in the sustainable security paradigm, quality of life is considered the focal point of discussions, and this concept implies the prevalence of conditions within which states respect citizenship rights. From this perspective, human security is one of the most important components for achieving reliable degrees of it (Abbaszadeh and Karami, 2011: 39). Additionally, attention to transcendent dimensions of security such as welfare security and meaning-oriented security, emphasis on comfort provision and freedom nurturing, the pivotal role of society in establishing security, priority of peaceful methods, emphasis on a positive, active, and agentive approach are among the most important components of the sustainable security paradigm (Zarghani and Bakhshi, 2016). The following table shows the differences between classical and sustainable security:

Table 1: features and indicators in the two paradigms of traditional security and sustainable security

Sustainable Security	Classical Security
Diverse threats: (economic, political, social, cultural, military, and environmental)	Mono-dimensional threats: (mostly military)
Diverse dimensions of security (economic, cultural, environmental security, etc.)	Mono-dimensional security
Multiple references: individual, society, government, environment, etc.	The main reference of security: Government and state
Focus on social development and human-centered policies (improving quality of life, citizen empowerment, poverty reduction, promoting civil society, etc.)	Security tools: force and coercion
The main role of society in establishing security (social capital, trust, participation, collective confidence)	Main role in creating security: Military force
Soft security tools: educational systems, negotiations, persuasion, agreements, etc.	Security tools: force and coercion
Problem-solving approach: prevention and addressing root causes (e.g., crisis of opportunity, structural conflicts)	Approach to creating security: Removing threats
Horizontal and long-term development: (from within; at local and national levels, focusing on sustainable peace and stable security)	Reactive and short-term development: (from above; focused on crisis levels)
Proactive and constructive approach: (diagnosis of causes, risk management, foresight)	Reactive and crisis-centered approach: (reaction to threats, lack of attention to causes and roots, confrontation through force and war)
Comprehensive and meaningful definition of security: (welfare, spiritual-meaningful, etc.) emphasizing mental peace	Minimum definition of security: (mostly physical and material existence)
Positive, free, and liberating peace: focused on development, necessary transformations, flourishing, and empowerment	Peace through status quo preservation

Source: Zarghani, 2016: 49

It is worth noting that various factors have played a role in changing the concept of security from the traditional approach to the new one. These factors can be divided into two groups. The first group includes twentieth-century developments such as globalization, the expansion of cultural, economic, and intellectual exchanges, and the emergence of a global society. The second group includes economic variables (economic wealth, economic exchanges, meeting economic needs, and the welfare of the general public), political variables (governance of a powerful system with popular support and approval by the people), media factors (having information and communication resources), and cultural variables

(expansion of global culture and the depletion of internal culture and cultural identity loss) (Fatehi, 2012: 107). The table below briefly compares the models of sustainable security.

Table 1: The components of sustainable security in various theories

Paradigms	Foundations and Roots	Basic Concept	Main Aspect of Security (Priority)	Approach to Security	Tool	Pillars of the Paradigm
Power-Centered	Realism	Power	Military-centered	External, objective	Military power	Power, deterrence, sovereignty, stability
Suitability-Centered	Constructivism	Fit in creating security	Multiple dimensions of security	Objective and subjective, norm-based	Development	Development, proportionality of dimensions
Cohesion-Centered	Traditionalism	Social cohesion	Economic, cultural, political, environmental, etc.	Internal, subjective	Identity-based cohesion	Identity, satisfaction, institutionalized social security
Balance-Centered	Islam	Social balance	Comprehensive	Internal, subjective	Religious training	Revival, faith, upbringing, balance, legitimacy

Source: Bagheri et al., 46:1393

In addition to sustainable security models, some scholars have explained different approaches to establish sustainable security in the world and have proposed four approaches: introspective, inclusive, requisites, and strategic measures (Rastegar Panah and Soltani Far, 2012: 102-103), which are briefly mentioned. In the introspective approach, to manage insecurity instead of confronting threats, one must identify and devise solutions for processes leading to insecurity and control these processes to prevent the spread of insecurity (Poursaeed, 2013: 27). The inclusive approach emphasizes the rule of pervasiveness of security and insecurity at the global level and believes that only when all members of the global community cooperate with each other to face security challenges, common and sustainable security will be achievable. The third

approach is the requisites approach, which emphasizes maintaining moral authority rather than relying on conventional power in achieving sustainable security, and believes in comprehensive efforts to manage threats and challenges to people everywhere (inside, outside, and around the world). Finally, the strategic measures approach believes that establishing sustainable security requires a three-stage process. In the first stage, prioritization, integration, and coordination of development policies with security are discussed; in the second stage, the implementation of a budgeting and wealth distribution system in the country in a way that leads to strategic investment in economic development; and finally, in the third stage, the integration of peripheral regions with the center and the creation of strong communication networks are discussed in such a way that the reality and feeling of marginalization and isolation among people in different regions of the country are eliminated, and local institutions in security management always adapt themselves to the overall strategy of the country (Rastegar Panah and Soltani Far, 2012: 103).

In the author's opinion, the above approaches do not have clear and precise boundaries, and therefore, establishing sustainable security cannot be contingent upon selecting one or two approaches, and it is necessarily required to move toward a combined application of all approaches. Thus, based on the introspective approach, the first priority in confronting a security threat or challenge is to recognize and combat the cause, not the effect. The inclusive approach makes establishing sustainable security contingent upon the participation and stakeholder status of all actors, and the requisites approach emphasizes the different nature of sustainable security and the role of soft power in its establishment. Finally, the strategic measures approach, with an emphasis on strategic planning, systemic perspective, and correct prioritization, addresses the proportion and logical relationship between security and development (Zarghani, 2019: 56). Therefore, it seems that establishing sustainable security in borders and border regions is contingent upon a combined approach and the application of components from the above approaches.

Research Method

This research, using a descriptive-analytical method and by referring to reliable library sources, seeks to examine and explain border security based on the indicators and considerations of sustainable security. In fact, the main question of the research is: what requirements and considerations are necessary for establishing security in the border and border regions based on the indicators and

criteria of the "sustainable security" paradigm? Accordingly, in the theoretical foundations section, while examining the concept of security and border security, the indicators and criteria of sustainable security based on the "sustainable security" approach and paradigm have been examined, and on this theoretical basis, the most important requirements and considerations for establishing sustainable security in the border and border regions have been examined and analyzed.

Research Findings:

Requirements and Considerations of Border Security Based on the Sustainable Security Paradigm: In the sustainable security paradigm, unlike previous paradigms, security does not merely mean the absence of threat. Rather, security equals a sense of safety and peace that can result both from the absence or reduction of threats and from the existence of equal opportunities for creating and nurturing human ethics and virtues. More precisely, and as shown in the image below, in the "sustainable security" paradigm, firstly, human security plays a fundamental and essential role, and secondly, human security is not limited to one or two specific physical or psychological dimensions but encompasses four important dimensions: The absence of threats to human survival, The existence of necessary opportunities to meet diverse human needs, The absence of vulnerability in various economic, environmental, political, social, and cultural dimensions, The existence of necessary foundations for increasing self-esteem and human values (Zarghani, 2017: 3). Additionally, sustainable security has the widest circle of inclusivity; on this basis, sustainable security is defined as security for all (individual, state, environment), at all levels (existential, welfare, and meaning-oriented security), in all dimensions (economic, political, environmental...), with everyone's participation, in all spaces, over time, with a positive approach (creating opportunities...), preventive measures, and preference for peaceful methods (dialogue, persuasion...) (Zarghani, 2019: 51)

Figure 5. Components and dimensions of sustainable security

Establishing sustainable security in borders and border regions requires consideration of specific requirements and considerations. The first and perhaps most important issue in this regard is the question of the reference of security. The reference of security answers the question: security for whom or what? In response, four different perspectives can be generally distinguished: regime security, state security, national security, and individual (human) security (Eftekhari, 2004: 34). In traditional security approaches, the state and political regime were considered the most important reference of security, and all efforts and actions were aimed at preserving and ensuring the security of the state and political regime. However, in the sustainable security paradigm, we witness a change in attitude toward the security reference; meaning that in addition to the security of the state and political regime, the security of individuals, society, and the environment is also considered, and on this basis, sustainable security includes environmental protection, respect for people's rights and individual freedoms, and psychological security. As Barry Buzan, who was once a staunch supporter of state authority in security, in his later views believes in the multiplicity of security

references and believes that the state is no longer the only reference of security, but individuals, transnational groups, transnational and sub-national non-governmental organizations, media, and terrorism are all references in aspects of security (Eftekhari and Nasri, 2002: 47). In the new security approach, the main goal is the security of people, and the security of sovereignty is emphasized to the extent that it provides a basis for establishing people's security. In fact, the security of sovereignty and the security of people are two sides of the same coin, and the strategies recommended for its establishment should be able to ensure the security of people's sovereignty in the long term (Fatehi, 2012: 107).

Based on this framework, in the discussion of sustainable security in border regions, at least two security references can be recognized. First, the security of the border itself; as a political-spatial phenomenon that, from the government's perspective, any insecurity in it can first threaten the security of border regions and then the internal and national security of the country. Naturally, governments try to ensure border security, mainly using military and law enforcement forces and hardware and software methods such as establishing border posts, implementing border closure plans, etc. The second reference of security is the security of border residents, which in the sustainable security paradigm, even has a higher priority than the first reference, and is discussed in detail in the following. Another important consideration in the topic of sustainable security of border regions is the nature and dimensions of this security. Security has a broad concept for which scholars have considered different scales and dimensions. In terms of scale, security ranges from the lowest level, namely the local and regional level, and then national, to supranational levels and scales such as regional and global security, and of course, in today's networked and interconnected world, security at the global scale is important. In the discussion of sustainable border security, primarily the local and regional scale of security is concerned, and even the national security of the country is largely influenced by border security. In fact, international borders are considered the first line of contact and encounter of countries with peripheral threats, and therefore, establishing security in these regions plays an important role in expanding the secure space within the country. Another component in the discussion of security in border regions is the nature and dimensions of security. Scholars have raised various dimensions for security, and in total, six dimensions can be envisioned for security, including military, political, economic, social, environmental, and cultural dimensions (Eftekhari, 2004: 9-38). It is obvious that in the discussion of border residents' security, all dimensions of security are important; however, the most important dimension is economic security, followed by other dimensions of security such as social, cultural, and environmental

dimensions. In the following, the requirements for establishing border security based on the sustainable security paradigm are examined in detail.

Changing the Security Reference in Border Security:

Despite some new perspectives and policies in border management and control policies, establishing security in the border and border regions has so far mainly been based on the same traditional security paradigms, specifically the "control paradigm." This means that insecurity can be eliminated or reduced through hardware approaches and the use of coercive force and military power. In this framework, the main reference of security has been the government, and more precisely, "border security" has been considered as the limits of territory and sovereignty boundaries of the state, not the "security of border residents." Based on this, all efforts of governments have been to counter unauthorized traffic, smuggling of goods, and any action that, from their perspective, causes insecurity in borders (dealing with crime and criminals) without extensively and fundamentally addressing the causes and contexts of these illegal behaviors (addressing the context of crime occurrence) (Zarghani, 2018: 6). However, the nature of the "sustainable security" paradigm is to create security by addressing the contexts of crime and insecurity. Therefore, in border regions as well, instead of dealing with illegal actions such as unauthorized traffic, smuggling of goods, etc., in the first stage, the causes and contexts of such criminal behaviors should be addressed, and by eliminating or reducing the effect of these factors, insecurity should be confronted. As shown in the image below, in the traditional security paradigm, the main keyword is "border security," and border security means preventing any illegal acts along a country's borders and legalizing movements. The main solution for ensuring security is using the full military and law enforcement capacity to deal with criminals and illegal travelers. In this framework, numerous police stations and centers are built, and a large number of law enforcement forces are engaged in protecting borders. Additionally, massive border closure plans and wall construction are carried out at enormous costs, and numerous hardware and software equipment are used for precise border control. Criminals are also immediately introduced to the judicial sector for punishment upon arrest.

Figure 6: Border security based on traditional security paradigms

Unlike traditional security schools and approaches, in the sustainable security paradigm, instead of merely dealing with crime and criminals, addressing the contexts of crime and insecurity is prioritized. Accordingly, establishing sustainable security in the border and border regions primarily requires ensuring the "security of border residents." In this framework, and as shown in the image below, in the discussion of security reference, the main priority is people, and more precisely, border security is achieved only through border development and the "security of border residents." Thus, governments are obliged to first provide a secure space for border residents in terms of economic, social, cultural, political aspects, etc., by implementing comprehensive development plans. Comprehensive development in border regions means that in border regions, we do not face poverty, severe deprivation and underdevelopment, unemployment, absence or weakness of economic infrastructure, lack or weakness of educational and cultural services, dominance of security atmosphere and dealing with citizenship rights, etc. Naturally, providing these facilities and services for border residents will have a significant impact on reducing their illegal actions such as unauthorized traffic, smuggling of goods, mischief, separatist activities, etc., and through this, "border security" will be achieved. Essentially, the geopolitical logic of the border dictates that protecting, safeguarding, and defending the country's borders as a fundamental value in line with exercising the right to national sovereignty, political

independence, and territorial integrity should be at the center of policy-making and strategic policy. This strategic matter will not be possible without having border management and secure borders where all members of society and the country, especially border residents, feel at ease (Heidari et al., 2012: 118). It should be noted that security and law enforcement action against professional criminals, smugglers, and dangerous outlaws at borders is necessary at all times. However, a distinction must be made between border residents who, due to deprivation and underdevelopment of border regions, are forced to engage in some criminal activities such as smuggling goods and unauthorized traffic for their livelihood, and the minority of dangerous criminals with records, professional smugglers, outlaws, etc.

Figure 7. The process of ensuring border security based on the sustainable security paradigm

Relationship Between Development and Security in Border Regions:

There is a direct relationship between the development of the border region, sustainable security of border residents, and border security. Thus, as shown in the

model below, any poverty, deprivation, and underdevelopment in border regions will threaten the healthy and peaceful life of border residents, and inevitably, in a reactive action and to escape from various threats such as unemployment, poverty, etc., they will resort to smuggling goods, drugs, unauthorized traffic, membership and activity in separatist groups, etc. These security-disrupting actions result in the loss of border security, and inevitably, law enforcement and border guards confront such actions. The securitization of space and security and law enforcement confrontations will create serious disruption in the development process, and thus, in a closed cycle, this defective process daily adds to the dimension of insecurity and underdevelopment of border regions. It should be noted that having border security and secure and developed border regions requires designing and implementing programs and plans to establish sustainable security on both sides of the border. On one hand, government programs and plans inside and in border regions, and on the other hand, a policy of good neighborliness and cooperation with neighbors (Zarghani, 2019: 82). In fact, the development and security of border regions of a territory are not limited to internal policies, plans, and actions, but alongside decision-making and planning related to the development and security of border regions, the role of active diplomacy and inter-country cooperation should be prominently considered. In this regard, cooperation in joint exploitation of resources, joint economic programs (in agriculture, industry, services), can guarantee settlement and inter-territorial development on both sides of borders (Rahmani Fazli and Saeedi, 2015: 29). Conversely, with the implementation of policies and actions in the direction of sustainable development in border regions, anti-security and illegal activities such as smuggling goods, unauthorized traffic, etc. decrease, and gradually the security atmosphere diminishes, and the possibility of expanding economic activities and normal living space is provided; as a result, the possibility of attracting investment, increasing population capacity, strengthening infrastructure is provided, and this issue, during a process, strengthens the cycle of development and security.

Figure 8. The relationship between development and security and underdevelopment and insecurity in border regions

Discussion and Conclusion:

Governments, in terms of the type of sovereignty and the relationship between people and rulers throughout history, are divided into three types of governments: tribe-centered, territory-centered, and nation-centered. In all these types of governments, from primitive tribe-centered to old territory-centered governments, the borders between governments have had a significant role and importance. However, it is from the Westphalian period onwards and with the gradual formation of modern states and independent countries that international borders, as emerging political-spatial phenomena, gain increasing importance and function. Today, almost all countries in the world have specific international borders with their neighbors, and the preservation and protection of international borders is considered one of the first and most important priorities of countries' national security doctrine. International borders of countries are considered the first level of contact between the government and surrounding independent sovereignties, and therefore, the existence of secure and stable borders or unstable and insecure borders with neighboring countries has a direct impact on the level of internal and national security of countries.

Throughout history, governments have employed various policies and methods to secure their borders, with particular emphasis on military protection of their borders. The existence of massive and very costly border structures such as the Great Wall of China, Hadrian's Wall, the Gorgan Wall, etc., shows how important securing borders throughout history has been for governments. In the contemporary era as well, governments use diverse hardware and software policies, plans, and methods to secure their international borders with neighbors. Implementation of costly border closure plans, establishment of modern border posts, employment of modern optical and electronic surveillance and control technologies, creation of prohibited areas and border zones, population evacuation of the border strip, implementation of border regions development plans, etc. are among these plans and actions. A very important point in selecting and employing these policies and plans is the type of government's perspective and, more precisely, their security paradigm. Accordingly, the nature of "security" and methods of achieving it differ in the classical security paradigms and the new "sustainable security" paradigm. Thus, in traditional paradigms, generally, the nature of security is objective, external, and negative, and both in terms of its provider and its reference, it has a one-dimensional nature, and on this basis, the most important security reference is the political system, whose vulnerability is through military threats, and naturally, security is achieved through the increasing strengthening of military power. In the new security paradigm, such as the Copenhagen school, firstly, security has an internal and positive nature; secondly, it has five dimensions: economic, political, social-cultural, military, and environmental; and finally, the methods of ensuring security are based on social and participatory approaches, preventive, and based on persuasion and satisfaction.

Establishing security in borders and border regions has been one of the main concerns of governments from the past until now, and along with evolution in the realm of thought and security paradigms, we are witnessing changes in border security policies, approaches, and methods. Thus, in line with classical security schools, in the past, the concept of "border security" was essentially more prominent than "border resident security." In this framework, border security has been defined as: "preventing any illegal acts along a country's borders and legalizing the movement of people and transportation of goods and domestic animals in compliance with legal regulations and through authorized border gates." In fact, border security is the result of the function of components such as "protection," "prevention," and "control." It is obvious that in such an approach, creating security requires establishing various military and law enforcement

systems to prevent any unauthorized traffic and smuggling of goods and to deal with border violators and criminals. For this reason, governments tried to strengthen their supervision and control power by using various methods of physical and electronic border closure, and to create security at borders by arresting border criminals and violators. In contrast to this view, the "sustainable security" paradigm is proposed for borders and border regions, in which the concept of "border resident security" is more prominent. The components of this paradigm are derived from new security schools such as the Copenhagen school and some Islamic perspectives, and in terms of nature, components, and indicators, it has fundamental differences with the previous paradigm. The most important feature and superior characteristic of this paradigm is its preventive approach; meaning that instead of dealing with criminals and crime, it confronts the contexts of crime.

This means that security in borders and border regions is achieved when, instead of prioritizing dealing with crimes such as unauthorized traffic and smuggling of goods, which are mainly carried out by border residents, the causes and contexts of these actions should be addressed. For example, the eastern and southeastern border regions of the country are in an unfavorable situation in terms of talents and biological resources, especially climate, which has a significant impact on the residence and employment of border residents. Due to these unfavorable living conditions, the population capacity of the areas is low, and investment in industrial and service affairs to create employment (based on an apparent cost-benefit analysis) is also not logical.

This situation has caused the eastern and southeastern border regions of the country to be in an unfavorable situation in terms of development and security indicators, such that the status of unemployment, poverty, and income in these areas is very unfavorable. In such conditions, naturally, a number of border residents, mainly in emergency situations and to provide the minimum basic necessities of life, engage in unauthorized traffic, smuggling of goods, fuel, drugs, etc. Law enforcement and border guards are also obligated to deal with these illegal and security-disturbing actions within the framework of their organizational duties. The experiences of past decades mainly show such confrontations; these types of law enforcement-judicial confrontations may reduce the problem of border security in the short term, but it is not a logical and sustainable solution. It should not be forgotten that with the death of a fuel or drug smuggler at the border, a number of unsupervised children are left behind who have no specific source of

income and will inevitably take the same path that their fathers took. Therefore, while emphasizing this important point that control and supervision of the border and dealing with legal disruptive actions is necessary and essential, this will certainly not solve the problem of border insecurity in a fundamental way, and it is necessary to improve sustainable development indicators in these areas with precise planning and implementation of development projects in border regions. With the existence of sustainable employment for border residents and a moderate income, the rate of unauthorized traffic and smuggling of goods by or with the cooperation of border residents will decrease dramatically, and border security will also be achieved. More precisely, sustainable border security will be achieved through the comprehensive and sustainable security of border residents in various economic, social, cultural, and political dimensions.

It is worth noting that creating and strengthening economic development infrastructure in border regions, considering the low and unstable population of these areas, is not logical based on economic perspectives relying solely on cost-benefit analysis, and therefore, the private sector does not welcome it. In this situation, it is necessary for governments to intervene and, in addition to direct investments, implement long-term financial, credit, tax, and other supports for investors in border regions. If this is achieved, after a while, border regions will exit their initial deprived state, and with increasing population and the possibility of attracting investment, other valuable and neglected capabilities of these regions will also be exploited, and the development process will accelerate. For example, many eastern border regions, especially the southeast, have unique agricultural, mining, and industrial capabilities, and the activation of these capabilities plays an effective role in the sustainable development of these regions. From another perspective, spending considerable costs on border closure plans and establishing numerous outposts and using modern border surveillance and control technologies and the like, without paying attention to the development of border regions, is in fact erasing the problem, and it is better to accelerate the process of development and establishment of sustainable security in these areas by replacing part of the governments' enormous costs in border control and closure sectors with costs for the development of border regions. Finally, it is necessary to mention that, based on the sustainable security paradigm, the participation of border residents plays a very important role in establishing security and will intensify the development process and its endogenous nature.

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